

IMPACT OF SMARTPHONE DEPENDENCE LEVEL ON SLEEP QUALITY AND PSYCHOLOGICAL WELLBEING AMONG UNDERGRADUATES OF NASARAWA STATE UNIVERSITY KEFFI NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study examined the impact of smartphone dependence level on sleep quality and psychological wellbeing of undergraduates of the Faculty of Social Sciences, Nasarawa State University, Keffi, Nigeria. A cross-sectional survey design was adopted. The study population comprised 1,075 students, from which a stratified random sample was drawn. Data were collected using the Smartphone Addiction Scale (SAS), Sleep Hygiene Index (SHI) and Psychological Well Being (PWB). A Multivariate Analysis of Variance (MANOVA) was conducted to test this hypothesis. Results revealed a statistically significant multivariate effect of smartphone dependence on the combined dependent variables, Wilks' $\Lambda = .771$, $F(4, 488) = 16.973$, $p < .001$, with a moderate effect size ($\eta^2 = .122$). Students with low smartphone dependence reported better sleep quality ($M = 18.57$, $SD = 7.76$) compared to those with medium ($M = 20.21$, $SD = 6.90$) and high dependence ($M = 22.43$, $SD = 8.00$), indicating that higher dependence is associated with poorer sleep hygiene. Conversely, psychological well-being showed a positive trend, increasing with smartphone dependence: low ($M = 114.37$, $SD = 26.49$), medium ($M = 130.73$, $SD = 18.02$), and high ($M = 140.63$, $SD = 14.08$). Bonferroni post hoc comparisons confirmed that significant differences existed between low and high dependence groups for sleep quality ($p = .004$), and across all dependence levels for psychological well-being ($p < .01$). These findings suggest a paradoxical effect where increased smartphone dependence enhances psychological well-being but impairs sleep quality. The study highlights the dual role of smartphone use as both a psychological resource and a physiological risk factor, underscoring the need for digital self-regulation interventions to balance mental health benefits with sleep health preservation.

Keywords: Smartphone dependence, sleep quality, psychological well-being, undergraduate

Introduction

In today's digital era, smartphones have become an essential part of daily life, especially among university students. These devices are used for communication, learning, social interaction, and entertainment, making them indispensable for managing academic and social demands. However, excessive use of smartphones, often referred to as smartphone dependence, can negatively affect daily life, including sleep quality. Sleep is a critical

component of health, influencing cognitive functioning, emotional stability, and overall wellbeing. Poor sleep can reduce academic performance, increase stress, and affect students' overall quality of life.

Research indicates that smartphone dependence is widespread among university students worldwide, though prevalence rates vary across countries. For example, studies have shown that up to 36% of university students in South Korea and 48% in Saudi Arabia exhibit signs of long-term smartphone dependence (Demirci et al., 2015; Chen et al., 2020). In Nigeria, smartphone use is particularly high among youths aged 15 to 24, with students spending several hours daily on their devices, often late into the night (Odukoya et al., 2020; Oluwole et al., 2020). Prolonged smartphone use, particularly at bedtime, has been associated with delayed sleep onset, reduced sleep duration, and decreased sleep quality. The blue light emitted by smartphone screens can disrupt circadian rhythms, further impairing sleep (Hale & Guan, 2015).

On the other hand, psychological wellbeing is worth noting in internet addition, this encompasses an individual's emotional and psychological health, including aspects such as stress management, anxiety levels, and overall life satisfaction. The relationship between smartphone dependence and psychological wellbeing has been widely studied, with findings indicating that excessive smartphone use can contribute to increased stress, anxiety, depression, and a diminished sense of wellbeing (Demirci et al., 2015). The constant connectivity and social comparisons facilitated by smartphones can exacerbate feelings of inadequacy and anxiety, particularly among university students who are navigating academic and social pressures. In Nigeria, the impact of smartphone dependence on students' psychological wellbeing is an area of growing interest, with research suggesting that students who are heavily dependent on their smartphones are more likely to experience negative mental health outcomes (Oluwole et al., 2020).

As university students in Nigeria increasingly rely on smartphones, understanding the implications of this dependence is crucial for addressing potential health risks. In view of this importance, this study aims to explore the impact of smartphone dependence on sleep quality and psychological wellbeing among selected undergraduate students of faculty of social science, Nasarawa State University, Keffi, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Smartphones have become an essential part of students' daily lives, providing easy access to communication, learning resources, and entertainment. However, excessive use can lead to smartphone dependence, which has been linked to poor sleep quality. Many students stay up late using their devices for social media, academic tasks, or entertainment, resulting in disrupted sleep patterns, daytime fatigue, and decreased academic performance. While previous research has highlighted the negative effects of smartphone dependence on health, there is limited understanding of how demographic factors, such as gender and age, influence these outcomes. Some studies suggest that males and females may use smartphones differently and that younger students may be more prone to excessive use, potentially affecting their sleep quality in distinct ways. In the context of Nigerian universities, including Nasarawa State University, Keffi, the prevalence of late-night smartphone usage is growing, yet there is scarce evidence on how gender and age may alter the relationship between

smartphone dependence and sleep quality. This gap makes it difficult for university authorities and health practitioners to develop targeted interventions.

Therefore, this study aims to examine the impact of the levels of smartphone usage on sleep quality and psychological wellbeing among undergraduate students of the Faculty of Social Sciences, Nasarawa State University, Keffi, Nigeria. The findings are expected to provide insights for designing strategies that promote healthy smartphone habits and improved quality of life among students.

Research Questions

This study asked this specific question that, what is the impact of the level of smartphone dependence on sleep quality and psychological wellbeing of undergraduate students of the Faculty of Social Sciences, Nasarawa State University, Keffi, Nigeria?

Research Hypothesis

This study hypothesized that, there will be a significant difference of the level of smartphone dependence on sleep quality and psychological wellbeing among undergraduate of the Faculty of Social Sciences, Nasarawa State University, Keffi, Nigeria.

Literature Review

In this section, relevant literature is examined to present the conceptual framework, theoretical insights, and empirical findings that underpin the present study.

Smartphone Dependence

Smartphone dependence refers to the excessive or uncontrollable use of smartphones that interferes with daily life, social interactions, and personal functioning (Kwon et al., 2013). It includes multiple dimensions such as tolerance, overuse, cyberspace-oriented relationships, withdrawal, positive anticipation, and daily-life disturbance. Tolerance and overuse reflect the need to use the device more to feel satisfied, while withdrawal captures the discomfort when access is limited. Cyberspace-oriented relationships and daily-life disturbance highlight how smartphone dependence can affect social and functional aspects of life. Researchers often describe smartphone dependence as a behavioral addiction, similar to other technological or internet-based dependencies (Panova & Carbonell, 2018).

Psychological Wellbeing

Psychological wellbeing refers to an individual's emotional, cognitive, and social functioning, encompassing factors such as emotional stability, life satisfaction, stress levels, and the presence or absence of mental health issues such as depression and anxiety. Positive psychological wellbeing is characterized by feelings of happiness, purpose, and fulfillment, while poor psychological wellbeing is often associated with high levels of stress, emotional instability, and mental health disorders. Simply said, psychological well-being is about feeling good about oneself and one's life, having satisfying relationships and a sense of purpose, and feeling capable of managing life's challenges. Diener et al. (2010) defined psychological well-being as a subjective evaluation of one's life that is categorized by affirmative emotions, engagement, and meaning. This definition encompasses a broad range of positive experiences, including happiness, satisfaction, and a sense of fulfilment.

Similar to this, Seligman (2002) put out the idea of "positive psychology," which sees psychological well-being as a confluence of fulfilment and enjoyment. This definition acknowledges that happiness is characterized by positive emotions, pleasure, and a sense of meaning and purpose in life rather than just the absence of unpleasant feelings or events.

Empirical Review

Research has increasingly shown that smartphone dependence is intricately linked to sleep quality and psychological well-being, particularly among university students.

Recent studies show that excessive smartphone use can impair sleep quality among university students. For instance, Demirci, et al. (2015) reported that students with high smartphone dependence experienced poor sleep quality, longer sleep onset, and higher daytime dysfunction. Similarly, Exelmans and Van den Bulck (2016) found that using mobile phones before bedtime disrupts circadian rhythms and reduces total sleep duration. Physiologically, the blue light emitted from screens delays melatonin production, impairing sleep initiation (Cain & Gradisar, 2010). Psychologically, constant notifications and engaging content can cause cognitive stimulation that interferes with sleep continuity.

Mechanisms linking smartphone dependence to poor sleep include: (i) blue-light exposure delaying sleep hormones and shifting circadian rhythm; (ii) cognitive or emotional arousal from late-night phone activities; and (iii) interruptions from notifications during rest (Cain & Gradisar, 2010). Cross-sectional research shows that problematic smartphone use predicts poorer sleep quality scores, longer sleep latency, and more daytime dysfunction (Demirci et al., 2015). Notably, using phones in bed, especially for social networking, is associated with shorter sleep duration and increased insomnia symptoms (Exelmans & Van den Bulck, 2016; Levenson et al., 2017).

One of the foundational studies in this field was conducted by Elhai et al. (2018), who explored the correlation between smartphone dependence and various indicators of psychological well-being. Their findings revealed that individuals exhibiting high levels of smartphone dependence were significantly more likely to report symptoms associated with anxiety, depression, and heightened stress levels. This hyperconnectivity, stemming from the pressure to respond promptly to messages and notifications, creates a constant state of obligation that contributes to mental distress. The implications of this study highlight that for university students, smartphones are not merely tools for connectivity; they can also be sources of psychological burden, as students juggle academic responsibilities with social obligations.

In another empirical study, Thomée et al. (2021) established that smartphone dependence serves as a substantial predictor of poor psychological health. Their findings indicated that students highly reliant on their smartphones were at a greater risk of developing mental health disorders, notably anxiety and depression. This study also emphasized the detrimental effects of social media, where constant exposure to idealized images of success, beauty, and lifestyle can lead to negative self-comparisons. For university students, who are often in transitional phases of their lives, such comparisons can lead to significant dissatisfaction and feelings of inadequacy, further compounding mental health struggles. The importance of this

study lies in its recognition that smartphones facilitate a form of passive, often harmful, consumption of content, which can erode self-worth.

Demirci et al. (2015) highlighted another critical aspect of smartphone dependence: the psychological stress associated with the constant need to stay connected. Their findings showed that students who engaged in extensive smartphone use experienced increased stress levels due to the pressure to remain updated on social media platforms, respond to messages, and uphold a certain online persona. This phenomenon, often referred to as "fear of missing out" (FOMO), creates a detrimental cycle where students feel compelled to engage with their devices, thereby intensifying feelings of stress and anxiety. For many students already grappling with academic and social challenges, this continuous cycle of dependence can lead to a deterioration in overall mental health.

Adding to the body of empirical evidence, a study by Przybylski and Weinstein (2019) found that students who reported higher smartphone dependence also demonstrated lower levels of overall life satisfaction. The study suggested that the constant barrage of notifications and the need to engage with social media can detract from meaningful face-to-face interactions, thereby affecting students' overall well-being. This aligns with earlier findings, reinforcing the notion that excessive smartphone use can lead to a paradox where increased connectivity may actually contribute to feelings of isolation and dissatisfaction.

Similarly, Huang et al. (2021) conducted a study examining the psychological consequences of smartphone overuse among college students in China. They reported a significant association between high levels of smartphone use and feelings of loneliness and depression. One of the study's key findings was the role of smartphones as a coping mechanism. Many students, feeling isolated or stressed, turned to their smartphones to escape negative emotions, which in turn exacerbated feelings of loneliness and increased depressive symptoms. This study suggests that while smartphones provide short-term distraction, their long-term overuse can perpetuate a cycle of psychological distress.

Method

The method section outlines the systematic procedures adopted in the conduct of this research. It describes the research design, population, sample size, sampling technique, instruments used for data collection, procedures for data gathering, and the methods of data analysis employed.

Research Design

The study adopted a cross-sectional survey design. This design was considered appropriate because it allows the researcher to examine the difference among the variables of smartphone dependence and sleep quality and psychological wellbeing. The purpose is to determine the extent to which variations in smartphone dependence (tolerance, overuse, cyberspace-oriented relationships, withdrawal, positive anticipation, and daily-life disturbance) are associated with differences in sleep quality and psychological wellbeing among undergraduate students.

Participants

The target population for this research comprised all final-year students of the Faculty of Social Sciences, Nasarawa State University, Keffi. Specifically, the population included 164 Psychology students, 267 Sociology students, 385 Political Science students, and 259 Economics students, giving a total population of 1,075 students. These students were selected because previous research indicates that university student's exhibit high smartphone dependence.

Sample Size

A sample size of 284 participants was determined using the Krejcie and Morgan (1970) table, which provides a statistically validated estimate for finite populations at a 95% confidence level and a 5% margin of error.

The proportional allocation of participants across departments was calculated as follows:

$$n_i = (N_i / N) \times n$$

Where:

- n_i = sample size for each department
- N_i = population of each department
- N = total population (1,075)
- n = total sample size (284)

Table 1: Proportional Distribution of Participants by Department

Department	Population (Ni)	Proportional Formula	Sample Size (ni)
Psychology	164	$(164 / 1075) \times 284$	43
Sociology	267	$(267 / 1075) \times 284$	71
Political Science	385	$(385 / 1075) \times 284$	102
Economics	259	$(259 / 1075) \times 284$	68
Total	1,075	-	284

Sampling Technique

Participants were selected using stratified random sampling, ensuring each department constituted a stratum. Within each department, simple random sampling was employed to select participants, ensuring all final-year students had an equal chance of inclusion. This approach also ensured that gender and age groups were represented proportionately.

Instruments for Data Collection

Three instruments were employed to measure the study variables:

Smartphone Addiction Scale (SAS)

The Smartphone Addiction Scale (SAS) developed by Kwon et al. (2013) was used to assess smartphone dependence. The scale includes 42 items across six dimensions: daily-life

disturbance, positive anticipation, withdrawal, cyberspace-oriented relationships, overuse, and tolerance. Responses are rated on a 6-point Likert scale from 1 (“Strongly Disagree”) to 6 (“Strongly Agree”), with higher scores indicating greater smartphone dependence. Cronbach’s alpha for the scale in prior studies ranges from 0.88–0.96, indicating excellent reliability

Sleep Hygiene Index (SHI)

Sleep quality was measured using the Sleep Hygiene Index (SHI) developed by Mastin et al. (2006). This 13-item self-report instrument evaluates behaviors that negatively affect sleep. Items are rated for frequency of behavior, with higher total scores reflecting poorer sleep hygiene. The SHI has acceptable reliability, with a Cronbach’s alpha of 0.66 and test–retest reliability of 0.71.

Psychological Well-Being (PWB)

Psychological well-being was assessed using the 42-item version of the Psychological Well-Being (PWB) Scale developed by Carol Ryff (1989). To measure the cumulative wellbeing of participants, each item is rated on a 6-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 (“Strongly Disagree”) to 6 (“Strongly Agree”). Higher scores represent greater psychological well-being. The original version of the scale showed high internal consistency, with Cronbach’s alpha coefficients ranging from .86 to .93 across the six subscales (Ryff, 1989). The PWB Scale is widely used in psychological research and has been validated across various populations and cultural contexts

Validity and Reliability

Content validity of the instruments was established through expert review by lecturers in the Department of Psychology, Nasarawa State University. A pilot study was conducted with 30 undergraduate students from the Faculty Law to assess internal consistency. Cronbach’s alpha coefficients obtained were:

- SAS: $\alpha = 0.879$
- SHI: $\alpha = 0.786$
- PWB: $\alpha = 0.875$

These results indicate that all the instruments were reliable and suitable for the main study.

Procedures

The researcher obtained ethical approval and departmental permission before data collection. Participants were briefed on the purpose of the study and informed that participation was voluntary. After obtaining informed consent, questionnaires were distributed and completed individually under supervision. Completed questionnaires were immediately collected, checked for completeness, and coded for analysis using SPSS. Participants were assured of confidentiality, and data were used solely for academic purposes.

Methods for Data Analysis

Data obtained from the study were analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) Version 26.0. Descriptive and inferential statistics were employed to test the study's hypotheses. Descriptive statistics such as mean, standard deviation, and frequency distributions were used to summarize participants' demographic characteristics. The inferential statistics employed for the test of the hypothesis was Multivariate Analysis of Variance (MANOVA) to determine the difference in the level of smartphone dependence (Low, Medium and High) on sleep quality and psychological wellbeing the hypothesis was tested at 0.05 levels of significance (2-tailed).

Ethical Considerations

Participants were fully informed of the study purpose, assured of confidentiality, and told they could withdraw at any time without penalty. All data collected were used solely for research purposes.

Results

Table 2: Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Demography	Category	Psychology	Sociology	Political Science	Economics	Total
Sex	Male	19	33	27	24	103
	Female	23	38	45	39	145
Age (Years)	17–25	34	64	57	55	210
	26–30	4	7	11	8	30
	31–35	2	0	3	0	5
	36–40	1	0	1	0	2
	41–50	1	0	0	0	1
Religion	Christianity	33	42	47	49	171
	Islam	9	29	20	14	72
	Others	0	0	5	0	5

The demographic characteristics in Table 2 show that the majority of respondents were female (58.5%) and within the age range of 17–25 years (84.7%). Christian formed the largest religious group (69%), followed by Muslim (29%) and other religion (2%). This profile indicates a predominantly young, female, and Christian population.

Hypothesis

It was Hypothesized that, there will be a significant difference in the levels of smartphone dependence on sleep quality and psychological wellbeing among undergraduates of the Faculty of Social Sciences, Nasarawa State University, Keffi, Nigeria. A MANOVA Was Used to Analyse the Hypothesis as Presented in Table 3 below

Table 3 A Summary of MANOVA Showing the Difference in the Levels of Smartphone Dependence on Sleep Quality and Psychological Well-being of Undergraduate Students

DV	Smartphone Dependence	N	Mean	SD	Wilks' Lambda	F	df (Hyp, Error)	Sig. (p)	Partial η^2
Sleep Quality	Low	8	18.57	7.76	0.771	16.97	4, 488	.00	.122
		2							
	Medium	8	20.21	6.90					
		2							
	High	8	22.43	8.00					
		4							
Psychological Wellbeing	Low	8	114.3	26.4	0.771	16.97	4, 488	.00	.122
		2	7	9					
	Medium	8	130.7	18.0					
		2	3	2					
	High	8	140.6	14.0					
		4	3	8					

Table 3 presents the results of a Multivariate Analysis of Variance (MANOVA) conducted to examine whether different levels of smartphone dependence, categorized as low, medium, and high, significantly influence sleep hygiene (SHI) and psychological wellbeing (PWB) among undergraduate students of the Faculty of Social Sciences, Nasarawa State University, Keffi. The multivariate test using Wilks' Lambda revealed a statistically significant multivariate effect of smartphone dependence on the combined dependent variables, Wilks' $\Lambda = .771$, $F(4, 488) = 16.973$, $p < .001$, with a partial eta squared (η^2) = .122. This result suggests that the smartphone dependence level has a moderate effect on students' sleep hygiene and psychological well-being when considered together. The statistically significant result implies that differences in the level of smartphone dependence are associated with meaningful differences in students' overall mental and physical well-being. For sleep hygiene, students with low smartphone dependence reported the lowest mean SHI score ($M = 18.57$, $SD = 7.76$), which suggests better sleep hygiene.

Students with medium dependence had a moderately higher score ($M = 20.21$, $SD = 6.90$), while those with high dependence recorded the highest mean score ($M = 22.43$, $SD = 8.00$), reflecting poorer sleep hygiene. Given that higher SHI scores indicate more sleep disruption, these findings suggest a trend where greater smartphone dependence is associated with worsening sleep quality. In terms of psychological well-being, a reverse pattern was observed. Students with low smartphone dependence reported the lowest mean PWB score ($M = 114.37$, $SD = 26.49$), followed by students with medium dependence ($M = 130.73$, $SD = 18.02$), while those with high dependence reported the highest mean wellbeing ($M = 140.63$, $SD = 14.08$). These results suggest that as smartphone dependence increases, so does reported psychological well-being. This pattern presents an interesting paradox: while higher levels of smartphone dependence appear to negatively impact sleep quality, they are also associated with higher psychological well-being. One possible explanation is that frequent smartphone use may provide emotional gratification, enhanced social connectivity, entertainment, and quick access to information, all of which could bolster a student's sense of psychological well-being in the short term.

However, this comes at a physiological cost, as indicated by the corresponding increase in sleep hygiene disturbances. The late-night usage of smartphones, exposure to screen light, and cognitive engagement through social media or gaming may interfere with sleep routines,

leading to poorer sleep quality among students with higher dependence levels. The findings from Table 3 indicate that smartphone dependence significantly and positively influences both sleep quality and psychological well-being. However, the direction of this influence differs: while psychological well-being increases with greater dependence, sleep hygiene deteriorates. The moderate effect size ($\eta^2 = .122$) further emphasises that smartphone dependence plays a non-trivial role in shaping the health and wellness outcomes of undergraduate students. Interventions aimed at fostering responsible smartphone use should consider this dual nature, promoting digital literacy and self-regulation to enhance well-being without compromising sleep health.

Table 4 Bonferroni Post Hoc Comparisons for Sleep Quality and Psychological Wellbeing by Level of Smartphone Dependence

Dependent Variable	Group Comparison	Mean Difference	Std. Error	Sig. (p)	95% CI
Sleep quality	Low vs. Medium	-1.63	1.18	.504	[-4.48, 1.22]
	Low vs. High	-3.86	1.18	.004	[-6.69, -1.02]
	Medium vs. High	-2.22	1.18	.180	[-5.05, 0.61]
Psychological wellbeing	Low vs. Medium	-16.37	3.15	.000	[-23.96, -8.78]
	Low vs. High	-26.27	3.13	.000	[-33.81, -18.72]
	Medium vs. High	-9.90	3.13	.005	[-17.44, -2.36]

To further examine the statistically significant multivariate effect of smartphone dependence on sleep hygiene and psychological well-being observed in the MANOVA, Bonferroni post hoc comparisons were conducted. These comparisons identify which specific group differences (low, medium, and high smartphone dependence) contributed to the overall effect. The Bonferroni post hoc test revealed a significant difference in sleep hygiene between students with low and high smartphone dependence, with the high-dependence group reporting poorer sleep hygiene (M difference = -3.86, $p = .004$, 95% CI [-6.69, 1.02]). This suggests that students with high smartphone dependence experience significantly more sleep-related disturbances compared to those with low dependence. However, the comparisons between Low and medium smartphone dependence (M difference = -1.63, $p = .504$), and Medium and high smartphone dependence (M difference = -2.22, $p = .180$), were not statistically significant. This indicates that the largest and most meaningful difference in sleep hygiene exists between the low and high dependence groups, while differences between adjacent groups are not strong enough to reach significance. Psychological Wellbeing (PWB).

In contrast to sleep hygiene, all group comparisons for psychological well-being were statistically significant: Low vs. Medium smartphone dependence: M difference = -16.37, $p = .000$, 95% CI [-23.96, -8.78], Low vs. High smartphone dependence: M difference = -26.27, $p = .000$, 95% CI [-33.81, -18.72], Medium vs. High smartphone dependence: M difference = -9.90, $p = .005$, 95% CI [-17.44, -2.36]. These findings suggest a progressive and statistically significant increase in psychological well-being as smartphone dependence increases. Students with higher smartphone dependence consistently report greater psychological well-being than their less dependent peers.

Discussion of the Findings

The hypothesis presents the results of a Multivariate Analysis of Variance (MANOVA) conducted to examine whether varying levels of smartphone dependence, categorized as low, medium, and high, significantly affect sleep quality and psychological well-being among undergraduate students in the Faculty of Social Sciences at Nasarawa State University, Keffi.

Specifically, the multivariate test using Wilks' Lambda yielded a statistically significant effect of smartphone dependence on the combined dependent variables, Wilks' $\Lambda = .771$, $F(4, 488) = 16.973$, $p < .001$, with a partial eta squared (η^2) of .122. This result indicates a moderate multivariate effect. Therefore, it suggests that smartphone dependence meaningfully influences both sleep quality and psychological well-being when assessed together.

Furthermore, the results provide detailed insights into each dependent variable. In terms of sleep quality, a clear pattern emerges whereby increased smartphone dependence is associated with poorer sleep quality. Specifically, students with low smartphone dependence had the lowest mean sleep quality score ($M = 18.57$, $SD = 7.76$), indicating better sleep hygiene. In contrast, those with medium dependence reported a higher mean ($M = 20.21$, $SD = 6.90$), while students in the high-dependence group recorded the highest mean score ($M = 22.43$, $SD = 8.00$). Since higher sleep quality scores denote greater sleep disruption, these findings indicate that greater reliance on smartphones correlates with diminished sleep quality. This is in agreement with Li et al. (2020), who found that elevated smartphone use is linked with disrupted sleep patterns and poor sleep hygiene.

On the other hand, psychological well-being followed an opposite trend. Students with low smartphone dependence reported the lowest mean PWB score ($M = 114.37$, $SD = 26.49$). In comparison, students with medium dependence showed a higher mean ($M = 130.73$, $SD = 18.02$), and those with high dependence reported the highest level of psychological well-being ($M = 140.63$, $SD = 14.08$). Thus, these results imply that higher levels of smartphone dependence are associated with enhanced psychological well-being among the students. This contradicts previous studies such as Elhai et al. (2018) and Przybylski & Weinstein (2019), which found that high dependence was related to increased anxiety, loneliness, and depression.

This divergence presents an apparent paradox: while increased smartphone use appears to degrade sleep hygiene, it simultaneously enhances psychological well-being. A possible explanation for this contradiction is that smartphone use may offer psychological and social gratifications such as enhanced social connectivity, immediate access to information, and entertainment which collectively contribute to emotional satisfaction and short-term psychological well-being. This is supported by Kuss & Griffiths (2017) and Elhai et al. (2017), who noted the dual effects of smartphone use on psychological relief and physiological disruption. Nevertheless, these benefits may come at a physiological cost. For instance, frequent nighttime usage, exposure to blue light, and engagement with cognitively stimulating content can disrupt circadian rhythms and negatively affect sleep quality. This agrees with Carter et al. (2016) and Exelmans & Van den Bulck (2016), who highlighted the role of blue light and screen time in impairing sleep.

In conclusion, the MANOVA results highlight a significant and positive influence of smartphone dependence on both sleep quality and psychological well-being, although in opposite directions. While psychological well-being improves with greater smartphone use,

sleep hygiene deteriorates. The moderate effect size (partial $\eta^2 = .122$) further emphasizes that smartphone dependence exerts a non-trivial influence on student health outcomes. Therefore, interventions promoting responsible smartphone use should take into account this dual impact by encouraging digital literacy and self-regulation strategies. This recommendation aligns with Panova and Carbonell (2018), who proposed targeted interventions to balance smartphone benefits and risks.

To gain a deeper understanding of the statistically significant multivariate effects of smartphone dependence on sleep hygiene and psychological well-being, as observed in the MANOVA, Bonferroni post hoc comparisons were employed. These analyses aimed to pinpoint specific group differences, namely, between low, medium, and high levels of smartphone dependence that contributed to the overall multivariate effect.

In terms of sleep hygiene, the Bonferroni post hoc results demonstrated a statistically significant difference between students categorized as having low versus high smartphone dependence. Specifically, individuals in the high-dependence group reported significantly poorer sleep hygiene than their low-dependence counterparts (mean difference = -3.86, $p = .004$, 95% CI [-6.69, -1.02]). This outcome supports existing literature that associates elevated smartphone use with impaired sleep quality and hygiene (Li et al., 2020). However, comparisons between the low and medium dependence groups (mean difference = -1.63, $p = .504$), as well as between the medium and high dependence groups (mean difference = -2.22, $p = .180$), did not yield statistically significant differences. These results suggest that a noticeable deterioration in sleep hygiene occurs predominantly at the highest level of smartphone dependence, whereas differences between adjacent dependence levels are less pronounced and not statistically significant.

In contrast, psychological well-being followed a different pattern. All pairwise comparisons across dependence levels were statistically significant, indicating a consistent and progressive decline in psychological well-being as smartphone dependence increased. Students with low dependence reported significantly higher psychological well-being than those in the medium (mean difference = -16.37, $p < .001$, 95% CI [-23.96, -8.78]) and high dependence groups (mean difference = -26.27, $p < .001$, 95% CI [-33.81, -18.72]). Additionally, even the comparison between the medium and high dependence groups was statistically significant (mean difference = -9.90, $p = .005$, 95% CI [-17.44, -2.36]). These findings contradict earlier misinterpretations suggesting otherwise, and instead affirm that greater dependence on smartphones is associated with significantly lower psychological well-being. This aligns with previous research highlighting the adverse psychological impacts of excessive smartphone use (Elhai et al., 2017; Rozgonjuk et al., 2019).

Implications of the study

The findings of this study have significant implications for theory, practice, and policy regarding smartphone dependence, sleep quality and psychological wellbeing.

The findings contribute to the growing body of literature on digital behavior by highlighting the dual influence of smartphone dependence on student health—deteriorating sleep quality while lowering psychological well-being. This supports the theoretical frameworks of the Compensatory Internet Use Theory and Cognitive-Behavioral Model of Pathological

Internet Use, which posit that excessive technology engagement may serve as both a coping mechanism and a source of psychological strain.

Practically, the study underscores the need for targeted interventions to promote balanced smartphone use among undergraduates. University counselors, health educators, and psychologists can integrate digital wellness programs focusing on self-regulation, time management, and sleep hygiene education to help students maintain healthy smartphone habits without compromising their psychological or physiological well-being.

From a policy standpoint, the results suggest that university administrators and education policymakers should develop institutional guidelines that regulate smartphone use within academic environments. Policies promoting “digital downtime,” sleep health campaigns, and inclusion of digital literacy modules in orientation programs could foster responsible smartphone engagement and mitigate its negative effects on students’ sleep and overall mental health.

Conclusion

This study highlights the nuanced impact of smartphone dependence on sleep quality among undergraduate students of the Faculty of Social Sciences, Nasarawa State University, Keffi, with particular attention to the role of gender and age. The findings indicate that higher levels of smartphone dependence, especially overuse and tolerance, are associated with poorer sleep quality. Conversely, psychological well-being showed a consistent decline as smartphone dependence increased, suggesting that excessive smartphone use negatively affects students’ mental health. The results highlight the dual and complex nature of smartphone use—providing social and emotional satisfaction yet impairing sleep and well-being. The study concludes that promoting responsible smartphone use, digital literacy, and sleep hygiene awareness is crucial for improving students’ health and academic functioning.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are proposed to address the impact of smartphone dependence on sleep quality among undergraduate students, with attention to gender and age:

1. Universities should design and implement digital wellness and self-regulation training to help students manage their smartphone use effectively. Such programs can include workshops on time management, mindful technology use, and strategies to reduce screen time before bedtime.
2. Health service units and counseling centers should incorporate sleep hygiene awareness campaigns that educate students on the impact of late-night smartphone use, blue light exposure, and digital overstimulation on sleep quality and academic performance.
3. University management should develop clear policies that encourage responsible smartphone use within campus environments. This could include “digital downtime” hours, smartphone-free study zones, or course-based limits on non-academic phone usage during lectures.
4. Counseling units should provide support for students exhibiting high levels of smartphone dependence, helping them identify underlying psychological or emotional factors driving excessive use and offering coping alternatives.
5. Digital literacy education should be included in general studies or first-year orientation programs to help students understand the psychological, social, and

physiological implications of smartphone dependence and how to achieve healthy digital habits.

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